

Article

Physical Activity and Health Habits of 17- to 25-Year-Old Young People during Their Free Time

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Abstract: The objective was to examine daily health-related habits and physical activity during free time in a group of young people, with the aim of analysing what types of habits are developed and the associations existing between these habits. A cross-sectional and observational study was carried out. The sample was composed of 1132 young people from Castilla-La Mancha (Spain), 53.4% women and 46.6% men, between 17 and 25 years old ($M = 20.63$; $DT = 2.01$). The instrument used in this study was the questionnaire of assessment of health-related habits (QAHH). Different ranges of age and gender were taken into account in the analyses. The results showed low rates of physical activity, with only 25% of the participants practicing physical activity in their free time. Regarding gender, no differences were observed between boys and girls in terms of the level of physical activity practice. The inferential analyses revealed several significant relationships between the habits of leisure time and the practice of physical activity. The analyses also revealed that alcohol consumption, tobacco consumption and Internet were used as means to escape from everyday life. The most frequent free-time activities of the participants during the week were the use of new technologies and the consumption of harmful substances. During the weekends the most frequent ones were physical activity and consumption of harmful substances. While the relationship between physical activity, health-related habits and leisure time in young people is complex, these results indicate that physical activity should be promoted in young people, especially during the week and as a healthy alternative to the consumption of harmful substances. To do this, professionals of different fields (education, psychology, sports sciences, nutrition and medicine, among others) should work together.

Keywords: leisure activities; lifestyle; physical activity; public health; obesity; diabetes.

1. Introduction

Previous research has focused on how people spend their free time, with the aim of knowing the behaviour of different populations during their leisure time. According to these studies, health has played an essential role in discovering if people use their time in activities related to health and if their daily habits are healthy. This research continues with this line of research, and it aims to analyse the main activities that young people practice during their leisure time and whether or not they are healthy habits. It is of utmost importance to mention the definition of health proposed by the World Health Organization [1], which makes reference to a whole state of physical, mental and social wellbeing. These aspects highlight the relevance of social, mental and physical dimensions [2].

There are recent researches in relation to the identification of patterns of physical activities which are positive for health [3]. More specifically, some recent studies have shown the association between habits of physical activity in young people and being physically active in adulthood [4,5]. Moreover, it

has been proven that lack of physical activity leads to obesity and health problems [6,7]. In the same way, other researches have studied the correlation between diet and the practice of physical education as factors that influence health [8,9].

Without any doubt, the practice of physical education contributes to the prevention of some diseases such as cardiovascular diseases, diabetes type 2, overweight and obesity, cancer of colon and depression and anxiety, among others. Moreover, physical activity contributes to the improvement of the psychological state of people. For this reason, it is of utmost importance to examine behaviours linked to health, with the main aim of explaining the current situation in society. So, the attention must be focused on some stages such as adolescence and youth, as they are essential in the acquisition of future healthy lifestyles [4]. Regarding gender, women practice less physical activity, and this inactivity increases with age [9,10].

The activities developed during free time are associated with fun, satisfaction and pleasure. However, these activities do not have to be related neither with physical activity nor with healthy habits. Within these unhealthy habits, smoking is higher in men and it increases with age. Furthermore, it is linked to lack of physical activity [11,12].

Bearing this in mind, it can be affirmed that alcohol consumption and smoking are associated with physical inactivity [13,14]. On the other hand, it has been observed that young women drink more alcohol in comparison with young men [15,16]. However, drug consumption is higher in young men [17]. In fact, the consumption of addictive substances among young people has generated concern. With regard to Spain, it is one of the leader countries in the consumption of these substances. All in all, consumption of alcohol, tobacco and drugs is linked to sedentary habits.

As well, the use of new technologies is considered to be one of the factors that influences physical activity in young people. Moreover, it is a barrier for the acquisition of the benefits that physical activity provides. According to gender, men spend more time using new technologies and playing videogames regardless of age [18,19]. On the contrary, young women spend more time watching television in their free time [17]. Furthermore, watching television is one of the most predominant habits in both genders [11,20–22].

For these reasons, it is essential to examine lifestyle habits of young people, which are very important for their health in future stages. Free time is the period of time dedicated to all those things that people do when they are not obliged to work or take care of others and themselves [23]. Without any doubt, free time is crucial for people owing to the fact that it is used to satisfy other basic needs, such as improving relationships and achieving personal goals. Therefore, the main aim of this study is to examine youth habits linked to practice of physical activity, alcohol, tobacco and drug consumption and use of Internet. Another objective is to know whether their habits are due to their desire to escape from their daily lives. Moreover, data will be analysed according to gender and age.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Design

The design of this study was cross-sectional and observational [24]. The relationship between habits of physical activity and consumption of alcohol, drugs and tobacco of a group of subjects was analysed. Gender and age of the participants were taken into account.

2.2. Participants

The participants were selected by snowball sampling. The sample was composed of 1132 subjects. Age, gender and distribution of the sample are shown in Table 1. The inclusion criteria were the following: Being within the age range of 17–25 years [17] and signing and completing the informed consent to participate in the study.

Table 1. Participants according to age and gender.

Age	Gender		Total
	F	M	
17–19	190 (51.8%)	177 (48.2%)	367 (100%)
20–23	360 (54.3%)	303 (45.7%)	663 (100%)
24–25	55 (53.9%)	47 (46.1%)	102 (100%)
Total	605 (53.4%)	527 (46.6%)	1132 (100%)

F: Female. M: Male.

2.3. Instruments

The questionnaire of assessment of health-related habits (QAHH) [25] was used for this study. To elaborate on this instrument, different questionnaires related to healthy habits were taken as references. Therefore, it is an instrument adapted from other questionnaires such as child and adolescents trial for cardiovascular health (CATCH) [26], screening measure for assessing dietary fat intake among adolescents [27], self-report measures of children's physical activity (SAPA) [28] and the scale of problematic uses of Internet in adolescents [29]. For the development of the questionnaire, previous studies about health-related habits were also considered [30–33]. The last version of the questionnaire is composed of 19 items with different answers and divided into six factors linked to health: Habits of free time, habits of physical activity, habits related to Internet and new technologies, smoking, alcohol and drugs. Moreover, it collects sociodemographic information regarding age, gender, level of studies and current position of the participants. The answers of the items are closed and categorized with different options, which range from 2 to 7 depending on each item.

The reliability of the instruments was measured through Cronbach' alpha coefficient and the value was $\alpha = 0.88$ (CI 95% = [0.864; 0.893]), which guarantees the reliability.

With regard to validity, given the qualitative-nominal nature of the items that compose this questionnaire, some usual statistics techniques such as confirmatory factor analysis were not calculated. On the contrary, alternative techniques such as expert judgment had to be used. To do that, seven experts who were highly knowledgeable about this field were selected. With the aim of validating this instrument, they had a questionnaire assessed by a Likert scale of three points (1 = low, 2 = average, 3 = high). The seven experts assessed the different sections and gave a global assessment (high = 85.3%). They also evaluated adequacy (high = 79.8%), precision (high = 73.2%) and relevance (high = 74.8%). In addition, a comparative assessment of expert accordance was carried out, with a Kappa concordance coefficient of ($\kappa = 0.78$; IC 95% = [0.762; 0.795]), showing accordance among experts.

Therefore, it is possible to state that this instrument is adequate, reliable and valid. Some changes in the wording of the items were proposed by experts to favour clarity and comprehension, and these were fully considered. Categories, variables and indicators assessed in the questionnaire are shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Variables, categories and indicators evaluated by the questionnaire QAHH.

Variables: Health-Related Habits	
Categories of the Variable	Indicators
Habits of free time	Time dedicated to free time during the week. Time dedicated to free time during the weekend. Practices to relax.
Habits of physical activity	Practice of physical activity. Practice of physical activity during the week. Practice of physical activity during the weekend.
Habits related to new technologies and Internet	Time dedicated to Internet during the week. Time dedicated to Internet during the weekend. Websites more visited.
Habits of consumption of tobacco	Habits of consumption of tobacco. Amount consumed daily. Difficulties in refraining from smoking in public places.
Habits of consumption of alcohol	Habits of consumption of alcohol during the week. Habits of consumption of alcohol during the weekend. Frequency of alcohol consumption.
Habits of consumption of drugs	Habits of consumption of drugs. Frequency of consumption of drugs. Weekly frequency of consumption of drugs Frequency of consumption of drugs during the weekend.

2.4. Procedures

The procedures of this study were developed in two phases:

1. During January, February and March of 2017, the participants completed the questionnaire, which was administered by five external collaborators in the street, in the vicinity of the university. With the aim of controlling strange variables, the researchers of this study selected them under agreement. The external collaborators had more than five years of experience in interviews and questionnaire administration. Moreover, the previous protocol was standardized and was distributed in a room with good conditions.
2. During April and May of 2017, data were analysed in relation to age, gender and categories.

2.5. Data Analysis

First, depuration and filtration of information were carried out, looking for errors of observation and registration and data irrelevant to the study. After that, inferential statistics were calculated. Chi-squared test was used to classify by gender and age. The intensity of statistics associations and size effect were measured by contingency coefficient. A level of 5% of signification was considered. In those relationships that were statically significant in the Chi-squared test, a “post-hoc” analysis based on Pearson’s residuals (Res) was carried out, in order to see which were the specific categories that were significantly associated. The statistical programs SPSS and R were used to process the data.

2.6. Ethical Considerations

Owing to the nature of the study, the declaration of Helsinki (2000), which establishes the ethical principles for the medical investigations in human beings, was followed.

Before completing the questionnaire, the participants signed the informed consent, where the objective and the confidentiality of this study were explained. Furthermore, this research was approved by the Ethics Committee of the University of Castilla-La Mancha.

3. Results

3.1. Descriptive Analyses

Table 3, from a descriptive approach through individual and total percentages, analyses the behaviour of participants in relation to the activities they practice in their free time according to specific time, age and gender.

Table 3. Use of free time according to specific time, gender and age (percentages).

Specific Time	Gender	Age						Total
		17–19		20–23		24–25		
		F	M	F	M	F	M	
During the week	Physical activity	2.39	2.39	4.60	6.28	1.06	0.97	17.68
	Study	4.95	2.92	8.49	2.83	0.53	0.71	20.42
	Shopping	1.15	0.62	1.68	1.50	0.62	0.53	6.10
	New technologies	4.60	5.22	9.11	8.75	1.06	0.97	29.71
	Harmful substances	3.71	4.51	7.96	7.43	1.59	0.88	26.08
	Other factors	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Weekends	Physical activity	2.8	3.9	9.2	11.5	0.8	2.1	30.4
	Study	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
	Shopping	3.2	3.2	4.9	3.6	0.2	0.4	15.4
	New technologies	2.5	3.7	4.3	4.0	0.7	0.7	15.9
	Harmful substances	6.1	4.0	11.1	6.0	2.2	0.8	30.2
	Other factors	2.2	0.7	3.0	0.9	0.9	0.3	8.2
Free time as a way of escape and/or relaxation	Physical activity	3.6	4.9	7.4	7.0	0.5	0.7	24.2
	Study	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
	Shopping	1.8	0.9	4.7	1.2	0.8	0.3	9.7
	New technologies	3.9	4.4	9.8	11.4	1.5	1.5	32.5
	Harmful substances	5.9	5.0	8.7	6.0	1.9	1.3	28.7
	Other factors	1.5	0.5	1.2	1.2	0.1	0.4	4.9

F: Female. M: Male.

3.2. Inferential Analyses

The tests used were the Chi-squared test, the coefficient of contingency and adjusted Pearson residuals. Table 4 shows the habits of physical activity, by age and gender, of the participants of this study.

In Table A1 (Appendix A), it can be highlighted that women from 17 to 19 years old showed significant relationships, of 95% confidence, between activities in their free time and number of hours practicing physical activity during the weekends ($\chi^2(8) = 37.541$; $p < 0.05$; $C = 0.534$). Concretely, the association between the hours of study during the week and the practice of physical activity from 4 to 8 h is relevant. On the other hand, in the same range of age and gender, there is a significant relationship between activities in their free time during the weekends and the usual practice of physical activity ($\chi^2 = 26.754$; $p = 0.001$; $C = 0.369$). Finally, in the same range of gender and age, there is a significant relationship between activities to escape from their routine and relaxation and usual practice of physical activity ($\chi^2(8) = 36.113$; $p < 0.01$; $C = 0.410$). It is of utmost relevance to highlight the significant relationship between consumption of harmful substances in free time as a way of escape from their routine and of relaxation, and the lack of practice of physical activity ($Res = 2.4$). Moreover, there is a significant association between the use of new technologies and the practice of physical activity ($Res = 5.1$).

Table 4. Habits of physical activity by age and gender (percentages).

Gender	Age						Total
	17–19		20–23		24–25		
	F	M	F	M	F	M	
Usual practice							
- Yes	3.9	4.0	12.0	14.2	1.8	1.6	37.4
- No	5.8	4.6	7.0	6.6	1.1	1.1	26.1
- No, I would like to practice it	8.3	5.5	14.4	5.5	2.1	0.8	36.5
Reasons for not practicing it							
- Lack of time	10.7	8.3	25.5	19.0	2.9	3.1	69.5
- Health problems	1.3	2.4	2.1	2.4	0.2	0.5	8.9
- Friends do not practice it	1.8	0.7	3.3	1.9	0.5	0.2	8.5
- Other reasons	1.0	1.7	4.8	4.1	1.0	0.7	13.1
Hours during the week							
- From 1 to 4	7.7	9.5	20.3	16.4	2.2	2.7	58.8
- From 4 to 8	3.1	3.1	6.9	14.6	2.6	2.0	32.3
- More than 8	1.6	1.6	1.6	3.6	0.2	0.2	8.9
Hours during the weekend							
- From 1 to 4	10.5	10.4	21.8	27.3	3.1	3.6	76.8
- From 4 to 8	2.4	1.7	7.2	4.2	0.6	0.6	16.8
- More than 8	1.9	2.0	0.5	1.3	0.2	0.6	6.4

F: Female. M: Male.

It was observed that the range from 20 to 23 years old is where there are more significant associations in relation to female gender. Therefore, there is a significant relationship between activities in their leisure time during the week and the usual practice of physical activity ($\chi^2(8) = 18.924$; $p < 0.005$; $C = 0.232$). Concretely, there is a relation between the use of new technologies and the lack of practice of physical activity, but with the desire of practicing it ($Res = 2.1$). On the other hand, continuing with the same range of age and gender, there is a significant relationship between the activities in free time during the week and the motive for not practicing them ($\chi^2(12) = 30.992$; $p = 0.002$; $C = 0.306$). Particularly, it was observed that there is an association between hours dedicated to study during the week and the lack of practice of physical activity because of the lack of time ($Res = 2.3$). Moreover, within this range of age (women), there is a significant relationship between the activities in free time during the week and the hours dedicated to physical activity during the weekend ($\chi^2(8) = 16.248$; $p = 0.039$; $C = 0.282$). Concretely, there is a correlation between physical activity practiced in free time during the week and the dedication of more than 8 h to practicing physical activity ($Res = 3.5$). Following the range from 20 to 23 years old (women), it was observed that there is a significant association between activities in free time during the weekend and the usual practice of physical activity. Moreover, there is a relationship between going shopping and the lack of practice of physical activity ($Res = 2.7$). On the other hand, there is a significant association between free-time activities and the motives for not practicing physical activity ($\chi^2(12) = 28.894$; $p = 0.004$; $C = 0.301$). Concretely, there is an association between the use of new technologies in free time and the lack of practice of physical activity ($Res = 2.1$). Besides, there is a significant association between the activities of free time during the weekend and the hours dedicated to physical activity during the weeks in the range of age from 20 to 23 years old ($\chi^2(8) = 18.446$; $p < 0.05$; $C = 0.325$). In particular, there is an association between going shopping and the dedication of more than 8 h to practicing physical activity ($Res = 3.4$). In the same way, there is a significant relationship between activities in free time during the weekend and hours dedicated to physical activity during the weekend ($\chi^2(8) = 16.271$; $p < 0.05$; $C = 0.289$). Specifically, there is an association between physical activity in free time during the weekend and the dedication of 1 to 4 h to practicing physical activity during the weekend ($Res = 2.6$). Finally, other significant associations are observed. There is a relationship between the activities of free time as a way of escape and relaxation from routine and the usual practice of physical activity ($\chi^2(8) = 50.774$; $p < 0.05$; $C = 0.364$). In this sense, the correlation between the consumption of harmful substances and the lack of

practice of physical activity is of relevance (Res = 4). Moreover, there is a relationship between the use of new technologies in free time as a way of escape from their routine and relaxation and the practice of physical activity (Res = 5.7). Furthermore, there is an association between activities in free time as a way of escape from routine and of relaxation, and the hours dedicated to practicing physical activity during the week ($\chi^2(8) = 23.139$; $p < 0.05$; $C = 0.357$). In particular, between physical activity in free time as a way of escape from routine and of relaxation, and the dedication of 1 to 4 h to practicing physical activity during the week (Res = 2.3). Moreover, there is a significant relation between consumption of harmful substances as a way of escape and relaxation, and the dedication of more than 8 h to practicing physical activity (Res = 3.5). To end with this range of age and gender (women), the existence of a correlation between the activities in free time as a way of escape from routine and of relaxation, and the hours dedicated to physical activity during the weekend must be highlighted ($\chi^2(8) = 19.864$; $p < 0.011$; $C = 0.309$). In a specific way, there is a significant association between the use of new technologies and going shopping in free time as a way of escape from routine and of relaxation, and the dedication of 1 to 4 h to practicing physical activity during the weekend (Res = 2.2; Res = 2.3). Moreover, there is an association between the consumption of harmful substances as a way of escape from routine and of relaxation and the dedication from 4 to 8 h to practicing physical activity (Res = 2.9).

In the range from 24 to 25 years old, continuing with the female gender, there is a significant relationship between the activities in free time during the weekend and the hours dedicated to practicing physical activity during the week ($\chi^2(8) = 15.788$; $p = 0.046$; $C = 0.607$). It is observed that there is no significant relationship between other activities in free time and the dedication of more than 8 h to practicing physical activity during the week (Res = 3.6). Moreover, there is a significant relationship between the activities in free time as a way of escape from routine and of relaxation, and the usual practice of physical activity ($\chi^2(6) = 17.132$; $p = 0.009$; $C = 0.505$). Concretely, there is an association between the use of new technologies in free time as a way of escape and relaxation, and the usual practice of physical activity (Res = 3.3).

Table A2 (Appendix B) shows the significant relationships according to the age of the participants between activities in free time and the practice of physical activity by men. It is measured by Chi-squared and coefficient of contingency.

With regard to men, in the range from 17 to 18 years old, there is a significant relationship between the activities in free time during the weekend and the usual activity of physical activity ($\chi^2(8) = 36.333$; $p < 0.05$; $C = 0.465$). The relationship between physical activity in free time during the week and the usual practice of physical activity is of relevance (Res = 5.1). Moreover, there is an association between the use of new technologies in free time during the week and the lack of practice of physical activity, but with the desire of practicing it. Furthermore, there is a relationship between going shopping in free time during the week and the lack of practice of physical activity.

Following with this range of age and gender, there is a significant relationship between activities in free time during the week and the practice of physical activity ($\chi^2(8) = 31.802$; $p < 0.001$; $C = 0.429$). Moreover, an association between going shopping in free time during the weekend and the lack of practice of physical activity was observed.

Continuing with the male gender, for the range of 20 to 23 years old there is a significant relationship between activities in free time during the week and the usual practice of physical activity. ($\chi^2(8) = 33.188$; $p < 0.001$; $C = 0.335$). Another relationship is between the use of new technologies in free time during the week and the lack of practice of physical activity, but with the desire of practicing it (Res = 2.7). Moreover, between the habit of study in free time during the week and the lack of usual practice of physical activity. On the other hand, within the same range of age, there is a significant correlation between the activities in free time during the weekend and the hours dedicated to physical activity during the weekend ($\chi^2(8) = 32.446$; $p = 0.000$; $C = 0.382$). Concretely, there is an association between study in free time during the week and the dedication from 1 to 4 h to practicing physical activity (Res = 5.7). Another significant association is between physical activity in free time and the dedication of 4 to 8 h to practicing physical activity during the week (Res = 3.4). Furthermore, following

with this range of age and gender, there is a significant correlation between the activities in free time during the weekend and usual practice of physical activity ($\chi^2(8) = 71.415$; $p < 0.05$; $C = 0.480$). A relationship between going shopping in free time during the weekend and the lack of practice of physical activity, but with the desire of practicing it, is observed ($\text{Res} = 3.79$). Moreover, there is an association between the consumption of harmful substances in free time during the weekend and the lack of usual practice of physical activity ($\text{Res} = 2$).

In the same way, there is a significant relationship between the activities in free time during the weekend and the hours dedicated to practicing physical activity during the weekend ($\chi^2(8) = 21.367$; $p = 0.006$; $C = 0.314$). Concretely, there is an association between going shopping and the dedication of more than 8 h to practicing physical activity during the weekend ($\text{Res} = 3.4$). Finally, for the range from 20 to 23 years old for men, there is a significant relationship between the activities in free time as a way of escape from routine and of relaxation, and the usual practice of physical activity. It must also be highlighted that the relationship between the use of new technologies as a way of escape from routine and of relaxation, and the usual practice of physical activity ($\chi^2(8) = 48.524$; $p < 0.05$; $C = 0.395$). Moreover, there is an association between the consumption of harmful substances as a way of escape from routine and of relaxation, and a lack of practice of physical activity ($\text{Res} = 2.4$).

On the contrary, there is a relationship between activities in free time as a way of escape from routine and of relaxation, and the motives for not practicing physical activity ($\chi^2(12) = 23.257$; $p < 0.026$; $C = 0.304$). In this sense, there is a relationship between activities in free time as a way of escape from routine and of relaxation, and the motives for not practicing physical activity. Another relationship is between the activities in free time as a way of escape from routine and of relaxation, and the hours dedicated to practicing physical activity. In particular, between physical activity in free time as a way of escape from routine and of relaxation, and the dedication of 1 to 4 h to practicing physical activity ($\text{Res} = 3$). Moreover, the significant relationship between the use of new technologies as a way of escape from routine and of relaxation, and the dedication from 1 to 4 h to practicing physical activity during the week is of utmost importance ($\text{Res} = 3$).

To conclude, in the range from 24 to 25 years old in men, it was observed that there is a significant association between activities in free time and the hours dedicated to practicing physical activity during the weekend ($\chi^2(8) = 17.300$; $p = 0.027$; $C = 0.598$). It is essential to highlight the correlation between going shopping in free time during the week and the dedication of 4 to 8 h to practicing physical activity ($\text{Res} = 2.6$). Moreover, there is an association between study in free time and the dedication of more than 8 h to practicing physical activity during the weekend.

Following with the same range of age, there is a significant association between activities in free time during the weekend and the hours dedicated to practicing physical activity during the week. ($\chi^2(8) = 32.255$; $p < 0.05$; $C = 0.738$). Concretely, there is an association between activities in free time during the weekend and the dedication of more than 8 h to practicing physical activity.

4. Discussion

The main aim of this research was to analyse the physical activity and health-related habits of a large sample of young people from Castilla-La Mancha (Spain). The analysis revealed that participants spent their free time practicing physical activity, consuming alcohol, using the Internet and smoking as a way of escaping from routine.

The findings showed that 25% of participants practiced physical activity in their free time. Previous recent research, such as the study carried out by Baños et al. [34], reported a higher number of people practicing physical activity. This could be explained due to the implementation of programs to promote physical activity from early years. In the study developed by Haug et al. [13], young people also consumed alcohol and tobacco, and this consumption was associated with sedentary habits. As José and Hansen [8] indicated, the association between physical activity and free time in young people is complex, as several variables should be considered, such as satisfaction, relaxation and pleasure.

In relation to gender, there were not differences between women and men in the level of physical activity. These results contrast with those observed by Li et al. [3], who highlighted that the levels of physical inactivity among women might be a worrying situation if an adequate promotion of health and the practice of physical activities were not favoured. What is more, an increment of alcohol consumption was also observed when the age of women increased.

Moreover, the findings of this study showed that lack of time was the main reason why young people did not practice physical activity. These results are similar to those found in other research [9]. In contrast, the association between physical activity and use of free time as a way of escaping from routine and relaxation was significant. This result is consistent with other studies [6,30], which showed that adolescents and young people practiced physical activity in their free time. Currently, there are many learning environments and strategies that are being built to favour physical activity [35–37].

The main strength of this research was the assessment of physical activity and health-related habits with a reliable and valid instrument in a large sample of young people of Castilla-La Mancha (Spain). However, this study also has some limitations. Due to its cross-sectional nature, it would be advisable to carry out longitudinal studies of health-related habits in young people in their free time during several years, with the aim of knowing if the behaviours found in this study are maintained or modified by the young people with time. Future studies should also consider if the participants are studying at university and/or living with their parents, and include young people of other regions. Finally, programs to promote physical activity and to reduce the consumption of harmful substances in young people should be implemented. These programs, adequately designed and tested, may be a very useful tool for those who are responsible for the education of young people.

5. Conclusions

The most frequent free-time activities of the young people during the week were the use of new technologies and the consumption of harmful substances. During the weekends, the most frequent activities were physical activity and consumption of harmful substances. While the relationship between physical activity, health-related habits and leisure time in young people is complex, these results indicate that physical activity should be promoted in young people, especially during the week and as a healthy alternative to the consumption of harmful substances. To do this, professionals of different fields (education, psychology, sports sciences, nutrition and medicine, among others) should work together.

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Appendix A

Table A1. Association between activities in free time and practice of physical activity among women (Chi-squared value and *p* value, contingency coefficient C).

	Activities in Free Time during the Week ^a			Activities in Free Time during the Weekend ^b			Activities in Free Time as a Way of Relaxation and Escape from Routine		
	17–19	20–23	24–25	17–19	20–23	24–25	17–19	20–23	24–25
Usual practice of physical activity	$\chi^2(8) = 9.962$ $p = 0.268$ C = -	$\chi^2(8) = 18.924$ $p = 0.015^*$ C = 0.232	$\chi^2(8) = 7.535$ $p = 0.48$ C = -	$\chi^2(8) = 26.754$ $p = 0.001^{**}$ C = 0.369	$\chi^2(8) = 61.178$ $p \cong 0^{**}$ C = 0.401	$\chi^2(8) = 12.163$ $p = 0.144$ C = -	$\chi^2(8) = 36.113$ $p \cong 0^{**}$ C = 0.410	$\chi^2(8) = 50.774$ $p \cong 0^{**}$ C = 0.364	$\chi^2(6) = 17.132$ $p = 0.009^{**}$ C = 0.505
Reasons for not practicing physical activity	$\chi^2(12) = 15.235$ $p = 0.229$ C = -	$\chi^2(12) = 30.992$ $p = 0.002^{**}$ C = 0.306	$\chi^2(12) = 9.104$ $p = 0.694$ C = -	$\chi^2(12) = 11.837$ $p = 0.459$ C = -	$\chi^2(12) = 28.894$ $p = 0.004^{**}$ C = 0.301	$\chi^2(12) = 14.872$ $p = 0.249$ C = -	$\chi^2(12) = 11.772$ $p = 0.464$ C = -	$\chi^2(12) = 13.555$ $p = 0.330$ C = -	$\chi^2(12) = 9.361$ $p = 0.672$ C = -
Hours dedicated to practicing physical activity during the week	$\chi^2(8) = 12.657$ $p = 0.124$ C = -	$\chi^2(8) = 12.241$ $p = 0.141$ C = -	$\chi^2(8) = 4.080$ $p = 0.850$ C = -	$\chi^2(8) = 7.063$ $p = 0.530$ C = -	$\chi^2(8) = 18.446$ $p = 0.018^*$ C = 0.325	$\chi^2(8) = 15.788$ $p = 0.046^*$ C = 0.607	$\chi^2(8) = 3.018$ $p = 0.933$ C = -	$\chi^2(8) = 23.139$ $p = 0.003^{**}$ C = 0.357	$\chi^2(6) = 7.741$ $p = 0.258$ C = -
Hours dedicated to practicing physical activity during the weekend	$\chi^2(8) = 37.541$ $p \cong 0^{**}$ C = 0.534	$\chi^2(8) = 16.248$ $p = 0.039^*$ C = 0.282	$\chi^2(6) = 3.563$ $p = 0.736$ C = -	$\chi^2(8) = 5.151$ $p = 0.741$ C = -	$\chi^2(8) = 16.271$ $p = 0.039^*$ C = 0.289	$\chi^2(6) = 8.618$ $p = 0.196$ C = -	$\chi^2(8) = 11.820$ $p = 0.159$ C = -	$\chi^2(8) = 19.864$ $p = 0.011^*$ C = 0.309	$\chi^2(6) = 3.906$ $p = 0.689$ C = -

^a During the week: From Monday to Friday. ^b Weekend: Saturday and Sunday. * Significant value $p < 0.05$. ** Very significant value $p < 0.01$.

Appendix B

Table A2. Association between activities in free time and practice of physical activity among men (Chi-squared value and *p* value, contingency coefficient C).

	Activities in Free Time during the Week ^a			Activities in Free Time during the Weekend ^b			Activities in Free Time as a Way of Relaxation and Escape from Routine		
	17–19	20–23	24–25	17–19	20–23	24–25	17–19	20–23	24–25
Usual practice of physical activity	$\chi^2(8) = 31.802$ $p \cong 0^{**}$ C = 0.429	$\chi^2(8) = 33.188$ $p \cong 0^{**}$ C = 0.335	$\chi^2(8) = 12.382$ $p = 0.135$ C = -	$\chi^2(8) = 36.333$ $p \cong 0^{**}$ C = 0.465	$\chi^2(8) = 71.415$ $p \cong 0^{**}$ C = 0.480	$\chi^2(8) = 8.515$ $p = 0.385$ C = -	$\chi^2(8) = 47.486$ $p \cong 0^{**}$ C = 0.503	$\chi^2(8) = 48.524$ $p \cong 0^{**}$ C = 0.395	$\chi^2(8) = 11.406$ $p = 0.180$ C = -
Reasons for not practicing physical activity	$\chi^2(12) = 11.915$ $p = 0.453$ C = -	$\chi^2(12) = 15.500$ $p = 0.215$ C = -	$\chi^2(12) = 13.136$ $p = 0.359$ C = -	$\chi^2(12) = 9.967$ $p = 0.619$ C = -	$\chi^2(12) = 6.878$ $p = 0.866$ C = -	$\chi^2(12) = 14.212$ $p = 0.287$ C = -	$\chi^2(12) = 18.865$ $p = 0.092$ C = -	$\chi^2(12) = 23.257$ $p = 0.026^*$ C = 0.304	$\chi^2(12) = 8.810$ $p = 0.719$ C = -
Hours dedicated to practicing physical activity during the week	$\chi^2(8) = 14.985$ $p = 0.059$ C = -	$\chi^2(8) = 32.446$ $p \cong 0^{**}$ C = 0.382	$\chi^2(8) = 12.167$ $p = 0.144$ C = -	$\chi^2(8) = 6.598$ $p = 0.581$ C = -	$\chi^2(8) = 9.022$ $p = 0.340$ C = -	$\chi^2(8) = 32.255$ $p \cong 0^{**}$ C = 0.738	$\chi^2(8) = 7.202$ $p = 0.515$ C = -	$\chi^2(8) = 25.240$ $p = 0.001^{**}$ C = 0.344	$\chi^2(8) = 13.295$ $p = 0.102$ C = -
Hours dedicated to practicing physical activity during the weekend	$\chi^2(8) = 7.155$ $p = 0.520$ C = -	$\chi^2(8) = 9.699$ $p = 0.287$ C = -	$\chi^2(8) = 17.300$ $p = 0.027^*$ C = 0.598	$\chi^2(8) = 8.745$ $p = 0.364$ C = -	$\chi^2(8) = 21.367$ $p = 0.006^{**}$ C = 0.314	$\chi^2(8) = 4.138$ $p = 0.844$ C = -	$\chi^2(8) = 9.823$ $p = 0.278$ C = -	$\chi^2(8) = 13.345$ $p = 0.101$ C = -	$\chi^2(8) = 9.047$ $p = 0.338$ C = -

^a During the week: From Monday to Friday. ^b Weekend: Saturday and Sunday. * Significant value $p < 0.05$. ** Very significant values $p < 0.01$.

References

- World Health Organization. *Informe Sobre la Salud en el Mundo 2013: Investigaciones Para Una Cobertura Sanitaria Universal*; WHO: Geneva, Switzerland, 2013.
- Pastor-Vicedo, J.C.; Gil-Madrona, P.; Prieto-Ayuso, A.; González-Villora, S. Los contenidos de salud en el área de educación física: Análisis del currículum vigente. *RETOS Nuevas Tendencias en Educación Física, Deporte y Recreación* **2015**, *28*, 134–140.
- Li, K.; Haynie, D.; Lipsky, L.; Iannotti, R.J.; Pratt, C.; Simons-Morton, B. Changes in moderate-to-vigorous physical activity among older adolescents. *Pediatrics* **2016**, *138*, e20161372. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
- Mäkelä, S.; Aaltonen, S.; Korhonen, T.; Rose, R.J.; Kaprio, J. Diversity of leisure-time sport activities in adolescence as a predictor of leisure-time physical activity in adulthood. *Scand. J. Med. Sci. Sports* **2017**, *27*, 1902–1912. [[CrossRef](#)]
- Eime, R.M.; Harvey, J.T.; Sawyer, N.A.; Craike, M.J.; Symons, C.M.; Payne, W.R. Changes in sport and physical activity participation for adolescent females: A longitudinal study. *BMC Public Health* **2016**, *16*, 1–7. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
- Cárdenas-Cárdenas, L.M.; Burguete-García, A.I.; Estrada-Velasco, B.I.; López-Islas, C.; Peralta-Romero, J.; Cruz, M.; Galván-Portillo, M. Leisure-time physical activity and cardiometabolic risk among children and adolescents. *J. Pediatr.* **2015**, *91*, 136–142. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
- Falbe, J.; Willett, W.C.; Rosner, B.; Gortmaker, S.L.; Sonnevile, K.R.; Field, A.E. Longitudinal relations of television, electronic games, and digital versatile discs with changes in diet in adolescents. *Am. J. Clin. Nutr.* **2014**, *100*, 1173–1181. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
- Jose, K.; Hansen, E. Exploring the relationship between physical activity and leisure in the lives of young Australians. *J. Phys. Act. Health* **2013**, *10*, 54–61. [[CrossRef](#)]
- Marques, A.; Sallis, J.F.; Martins, J.; Diniz, J.; Carreiro Da Costa, F. Correlates of urban children's leisure-time physical activity and sedentary behaviors during school days. *Am. J. Hum. Biol.* **2014**, *26*, 407–412. [[CrossRef](#)]
- Tannehill, D.; MacPhail, A.; Walsh, J.; Woods, C. What young people say about physical activity: The Children's Sport Participation and Physical activity (CSPPA) study. *Sport Educ. Soc.* **2015**, *20*, 442–462. [[CrossRef](#)]
- Ruiz-Juan, F.; Isorna-Folgar, M.; Ruiz-Risueño Abad, J.; Vaquero-Cristóbal, R. Consumo e ingesta de alcohol en españoles mayores de 16 años y su relación con la actividad físico-deportiva, la familia y el consumo de tabaco. *Revista Iberoamericana de Psicología del Ejercicio y el Deporte* **2014**, *9*, 339–372.
- Ahuber, L.; Vogel, M.; Grafe, N.; Kiess, W.; Poulain, T. Leisure Activities of Healthy Children and Adolescents. *Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health* **2019**, *16*, 2078. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
- Haug, S.; Schaub, M.P.; Salis Gross, C.; John, U.; Meyer, C. Predictors of hazardous drinking, tobacco smoking and physical inactivity in vocational school students. *BMC Public Health* **2013**, *13*, 475. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
- Dodge, T.; Clarke, P.; Dwan, R. The relationship between physical activity and alcohol use among adults in the United States: A systematic review of the literature. *Am. J. Health Promot.* **2017**, *31*, 97–108. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
- Sampasa-Kanynga, H.; Chaput, J.P. Use of social networking sites and alcohol consumption among adolescents. *Public Health* **2016**, *139*, 88–95. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
- Moinuddin, A.; Goel, A.; Saini, S.; Bajpai, A.; Misra, R. Alcohol consumption and gender: A critical review. *J. Psychol. Psychother.* **2016**, *6*, 1–4. [[CrossRef](#)]
- Guillén, N.; Roth, E.; Alfaro, A.; Fernández, E. Youth alcohol drinking behavior: Associated risk and protective factors. *Revista Iberoamericana Psicología y Salud* **2015**, *6*, 53–63. [[CrossRef](#)]
- Durkee, T.; Kaess, M.; Carli, V.; Parzer, P.; Wasserman, C.; Floderus, B.; Apter, A.; Balazs, J.; Barzilay, S.; Bobes, J.; et al. Prevalence of pathological internet use among adolescents in Europe: Demographic and social factors. *Addiction* **2012**, *107*, 2210–2222. [[CrossRef](#)]
- Sánchez-Antelo, V. La dimensión temporal del consumo de drogas: Análisis sociológico desde una categoría clave para el estudio de los procesos de salud-enfermedad-atención-cuidado. *Salud Colect.* **2016**, *12*, 41–54. [[CrossRef](#)]
- Bucksch, J.; Sigmundova, D.; Hamrik, Z.; Troped, P.J.; Melkevik, O.; Ahluwalia, N.; Borraccino, A.; Tynjälä, J.; Kalman, M.; Inchley, J. International trends in adolescent screen-time behaviors from 2002 to 2010. *J. Adolesc. Health* **2016**, *58*, 417–425. [[CrossRef](#)]

21. Mielgo-Ayuso, J.; Aparicio-Ugarriza, R.; Castillo, A.; Ruiz, E.; Avila, J.M.; Aranceta-Bartrina, J.; Gil, A.; Ortega, R.M.; Serra-Majem, L.; Varela-Moreiras, G.; et al. Sedentary behavior among Spanish children and adolescents: Findings from the ANIBES study. *BMC Public Health* **2017**, *17*, 94. [[CrossRef](#)]
22. Gil-Madrona, P.; González Villora, S.; Vicedo, P.; Carlos, J.; Fernández Bustos, J.G. Actividad física y hábitos relacionados con la salud en los jóvenes: Estudio en España. *Reflexiones* **2010**, *11*, 147–161.
23. Stearns, P. (Ed.) *A Day in the Life: Studying Daily Life through History*; Greenwood Press: Westport, CT, USA, 2005.
24. Montero, I.; León, O.G. A guide for naming research studies in Psychology. *Int. J. Clin. Health Psychol.* **2007**, *7*, 847–862.
25. Gil-Madrona, P.; Prieto-Ayuso, A.; Silva, S.A.; Serra-Olivares, J.; Jurado, M.Á.; Díaz-Suárez, A. Hábitos y comportamientos relacionados con la salud de los adolescentes en su tiempo de ocio. *Anales de Psicología* **2019**, *35*, 140–147. [[CrossRef](#)]
26. Perry, C.L.; Stone, E.J.; Parcel, G.S.; Ellison, R.C.; Nader, P.R.; Webber, L.S.; Luepker, R.V. School-based cardiovascular health promotion: The child and adolescent trial for cardiovascular health (CATCH). *J. Sch. Health* **1990**, *60*, 406–413. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
27. Prochaska, J.J.; Sallis, J.F.; Rupp, J. Screening measure for assessing dietary fat intake among adolescents. *Prev. Med.* **2001**, *33*, 699–706. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
28. Sallis, J.F. Self-report measures of children’s physical activity. *J. Sch. Health* **1991**, *61*, 215–219. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
29. Rial, A.; Gómez, P.; Isorna, M.; Araujo, M.; Varela, J. PIUS-A: Problematic Internet Use Scale In Adolescents. Development And Psychometric Validation. *Adicciones* **2015**, *27*, 47–63.
30. García, M.E.; Gómez, M.; Ruiz, F. *Hábitos Físicos-Deportivos en Centros Escolares y Universitarios*; Gymnos: Madrid, Spain, 2005.
31. Míguez, M.C.; Becoña, E. ¿El consumo de cigarrillos y alcohol se relaciona con el consumo de cánnabis y el juego problema en adolescentes españoles? *Adicciones* **2015**, *27*, 8–16. [[CrossRef](#)]
32. Muñoz-Rivas, M.J.; Navarro, M.P.; Ortega, N. Patrones de uso de Internet en población universitaria española. *Adicciones* **2003**, *15*, 137–144. [[CrossRef](#)]
33. Rodríguez, J.; Agulló, E.; Agulló, M.S. Jóvenes, fin de semana y uso recreativo de drogas: Evolución y tendencias del ocio juvenil. *Adicciones* **2003**, *15*, 7–34. [[CrossRef](#)]
34. Baños, R.; Ruiz-Juan, F.; Baena-Extremera, A.; García-Montes, M.; Ortiz-Camacho, M. Leisure-time physical activity in relation to the stages of changes and achievement goals in adolescents: Comparative study of students in Spain, Costa Rica, and Mexico. *Sustainability* **2018**, *10*, 2581. [[CrossRef](#)]
35. Kopcakova, J.; Dankulinova Veselska, Z.; Madarasova Geckova, A.; Bucksch, J.; Nalecz, H.; Sigmundova, D.; Van Dijk, J.P.; Reijneveld, S.A. Is a perceived activity-friendly environment associated with more physical activity and fewer screen-based activities in adolescents? *Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health* **2017**, *14*, 39. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
36. López Sánchez, G.F.; Gordon, D.; Hodgson, L.; Stubbs, B.; Gardner, B.; Smith, L. The effect of the 2016 Rio de Janeiro Olympics on spectators’ physical activity. *Atena J. Sports Sci.* **2019**, *1*, 1–8.
37. Trott, M.; Smith, L. What are the associations between extroversion, enjoyment, and wellness in group vs non-group physical activity? A pilot study. *Atena J. Sports Sci.* **2019**, *1*, 1–11.

